

BACTERIOPHAGES AS ALTERNATIVE THERAPEUTIC AGENTS TO ANTIBIOTICS

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Abstract. *The escalating global prevalence of antibiotic resistance highlights its role among leading health threats. According to WHO, CDC, as well as, major medical journals in 2019, nearly 5 million deaths were associated with antimicrobial resistance (AMR) with the heaviest burden falling on low- and middle-income countries. Significant AMR is paralleled by the rise of various reasons including medical practices (overprescription or self-medication; slow diagnostic paralleled by broad-spectrum antibiotics, which accelerate resistance), agricultural factors (growth promotion and disease prevention of animal stock by antibiotic usage), biological causes (natural adaptation and selective pressure to bacteria), as well as, scientific and economic challenges (increase in simple modification of existing antibiotics instead of development of new types). The worldwide antibiotic crisis has triggered a renaissance in bacteriophage research, highlighting bacteriophages as promising therapeutic agents.*

Objective: *This study aims to evaluate and compare efficacy of bacteriophage therapy with conventional antibiotic therapy. The review will examine the outcomes of bacteriophage monotherapy, antibiotic monotherapy, and combined bacteriophage–antibiotic therapy, with the objective of determining which approach demonstrates superior effectiveness in combating bacterial infections.*

Methods: *A narrative review of available clinical and preclinical studies was conducted, with emphasis on the antimicrobial effect with least side effects elicited by bacteriophages and antibiotics.*

Key words: *bacteriophages, antibiotics, Resistant Bacteria, Evolutionary adaptability, Phage monotherapy.*

Introduction. In the early 20th century, attention turned to agents with bacteriolytic properties. Western countries, the United States, and Russia seriously considered bacteriophages as antimicrobial agents and used them widely. Although interest in former antimicrobial agents significantly declined after the antibiotic revolution, the current problem of antibiotic resistance, as well as, their limited effects, have emerged bacteriophages as a promising alternative or complementary therapeutic approach. Classical representatives of bacteriophages consist of capsid (protective shell, containing nucleic acid) enclosing genetic material (dsDNA, ds/ssRNA), tail (injecting genome) and tail fibers (receptor-binding proteins, mediate bacterial specificity). This structural composition of phages provide stability depending on pH, temperature, and medium that serves as an important practical detail for therapy and formulation. Phage genomes exhibit considerable diversity, ranging from very small (~5 kb) to huge “jumbo phages” (>500 kb). Some carry accessory genes (e.g., toxins, virulence factors, or metabolic genes), which facilitates evaluating safety in therapy. Additionally, bacteriophages present co-evolution with

"complementary" bacteria due to CRISPR-Cas systems of bacteria in comparison to phage counter-adaptations. This dynamic makes them powerful natural regulators of bacterial populations. According to the International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses (ICTV), bacteriophages are classified based on morphology and life cycle. Based on morphology there are two groups: tailed phages and filamentous phages. Based on life cycle: lytic phages (infect, replicate, lyse host) or lysogenic phages (integrate into host genome as prophage, replicate passively until induced to enter lytic cycle).

Discussion: Advantages of bacteriophage therapy. Bacteriophages offer significant advantages over antibiotics due to several distinct factors which include targeted killing, activity against resistant bacteria, biofilm penetration, self-amplifying effect, as well as, evolutionary adaptability. Targeted killing. Targeted killing skills help to infect only specific bacterial species or even strains, which means they kill the pathogen without harming beneficial microbiota (unlike broad-spectrum antibiotics). Hyman P, Abedon ST. in 2010 summarized many lab studies showing phages typically infect only a narrow range of bacterial strains, often restricted to one species or even a subset of strains. Phage therapy against *Acinetobacter baumannii* infection (Schooley RT, et al., 2017) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Chan BK, et al., 2018) revealed precise targeting, without damage to other bacterial populations or human cells. Biofilm penetration. Sutherland IW analyzed phage depolymerase impact on biofilm matrices by in vitro and enzymatic laboratory-work, achieving expected success. Donlan RM conducted in vitro experimental models of biofilm destruction of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. All reviews and experiments showed that phage application reduced biofilm biomass and viable cells. Modeling and literature indicated that phage penetration depends on biofilm density, maturity, and bacterial physiology: younger, active biofilms are more easily penetrated, whereas older ones are more resistant but can still be reduced by phage enzymes and stepwise infection. Self-amplification. Self-amplifying effect describes phage replication as long as host bacteria are present and dose increases naturally until the infection is controlled. Payne and Jansen modeled mathematical pharmacokinetic/pharmacodynamic (PK/PD) principles in animal models and experimentally confirmed that phage concentrations rise as bacteria are present, essentially "auto-dosing." Mathematical and experimental modeling of Cairns BJ, showed phage population growth is proportional to bacterial density, confirming self-amplification. Dedrick et al. engineered bacteriophages for treatment of a patient with a disseminated drug-resistant *Mycobacterium abscessus*. Monitoring showed that phages persisted and replicated at infection sites, correlating with clinical improvement. This self-replication also aids in biofilm penetration by thickening phage layers leading to progressive inward movement.

Activity against Resistant Bacteria. First modern UK clinical trial of phage therapy against chronic *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ear infections resistant to antibiotics was conducted by Wright A. Treatment demonstrated significant reduction of bacterial load and improved symptoms. In 2018 (Pirnay JP et al.), review in addition to case series of phage therapy in multidrug-resistant (MDR) *Pseudomonas*, *Acinetobacter*, and *Klebsiella*, confirmed that personalised phages rescued patients where antibiotics failed. In vitro and animal models (Oechslin F., 2018) of phage-antibiotic combinations against MDR *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Findings presented death of resistant bacteria but also phage synergy with antibiotics to prevent resistance regrowth.

Evolutionary adaptability. Torres-Barceló & Hochberg (2016) emphasized their rapid co-evolution alongside bacterial resistance, while Burmeister & Turner (2020) highlighted real-time phage adaptation to overcome CRISPR-Cas defenses and receptor mutations. Clinically, Dedrick

et al. (2019) demonstrated the therapeutic potential of evolved and engineered phages in treating multidrug-resistant *Mycobacterium abscessus*, underscoring both natural adaptability and the promise of engineering for combating resistance.

Other benefits. Case reports (Schooley et al., 2017) showed phage cocktails eliminated infection without disturbing gut flora, minimizing dysbiosis risk. Early trials (NIH/ARLG, 2022) confirmed safety and tolerability in cystic fibrosis patients. Moreover, phages enhance antibiotic efficacy: Gordillo-Altamirano et al. (2022) demonstrated synergy against MDR *A. baumannii*, where phage-resistant strains became resensitized to antibiotics, highlighting therapeutic complementarity.

Limitations of bacteriophage therapy. Nevertheless, the opposing viewpoint warrants attention. Although specificity of bacteriophages keep surrounding tissue untouched, it leads to a narrow host range. The review of therapeutic phage biology by Hyman P (2019) explained limitations behind the high specificity and stated that it limits general use, requiring precise phage–pathogen matching or cocktails. Another limitation is associated with pharmacokinetics and delivery issues. In 2003, Payne RJH with Jansen VAA modeled phage therapy PK, which showed rapid clearance by spleen and liver, hence hindering efficacy unless bacterial load sustains phage replication. Merrill CR et al (1996). engineered phages that persist longer in circulation, after noting that wild-type phages were quickly removed by the reticuloendothelial system. Although findings presented susceptibility to removal, they highlighted that potential engineering modifications may resolve the issue. Yet, another constraint emerges during further experiments. Repeated phage exposure (Dabrowska K) induced IgM/IgG antibodies against capsid proteins, reducing efficacy via neutralization; Majewska J likewise showed stronger antibody responses after systemic than oral administration in mice. Additional limits include bacterial resistance through receptor changes, restriction–modification and CRISPR–Cas systems (Oechslin F), plus lack of standardized manufacturing and quality control. Most available studies remain small-scale, case-based or underpowered RCTs.

Comparison of antibiotic and bacteriophage therapies. *Phage monotherapy.* Comparison of phage therapy to antibiotic treatment presented that phages can be as effective, especially against resistant strains. During comparison monotherapies against chronic otitis due to MDR *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* by Wright A. and others, phages overperformed antibiotics showing reduction of bacterial load and symptoms. Several animal models including Oechslin F. (2018) study on endocarditis by MDR *P. aeruginosa* and Chan BK et al. (2018) on mice infected with antibiotic-resistant *Pseudomonas*, prove similar effectiveness of phages and antibiotics and rescue of lethally infected mice, relatively.

Antibiotic monotherapy. However, a randomized, double blind trial in Bangladesh (Sarker SA et al., 2016) implemented monotherapies on children with acute bacterial diarrhea (*E. coli*, *Shigella*). While phages were safe, clinical improvement was faster and more consistent in children receiving antibiotics, shortening diarrhea duration. Bruttin A and others, prescribed oral *T4 phage* to healthy human volunteers found that phages passed safely through the gut, but failed to establish high activity or reduce natural *E. coli* flora, unlike antibiotics that consistently modify flora. Another randomized controlled trial of phage against standard care antibiotics for chronic venous leg ulcers infected with *P. aeruginosa*, antibiotics standard care improved wound healing more consistently in comparison to phage therapy.

Combination therapy. Dedrick et al. reported favorable responses in 55% of 20 patients with *Mycobacterium abscessus* when phages were combined with antibiotics. A systematic review of 27 articles involving 165 patients reported a 100% success rate in those receiving

phage therapy combined with antibiotics (~21% of cases), compared with 81% success for phage monotherapy (~79% of cases). Similarly, in the UK chronic otitis trial (Wright et al., 2009), phage-treated patients achieved a 50% reduction in symptom scores, compared with 20% in the placebo group.

Conclusion. Bacteriophage therapy stands out from antibiotics through its narrow, targeted action, ability to disrupt biofilms, self-amplification at infection sites, and efficacy against multidrug-resistant bacteria. These properties also allow synergy with antimicrobial agents. However, limitations such as restricted host range, pharmacokinetic challenges, immune responses, and lack of standardized production remain. Evidence shows that while phage monotherapy can match or surpass antibiotics in some cases, combination regimens are especially promising. In Uzbekistan, where antibiotic-resistant infections are rising, expanding research, clinical trials, and integration of phage therapy into the national health system represents a timely and strategic opportunity.